

CP1: MtrunA17_Chr0c01g0489091

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

ncRNA: MtrunA17_Chr0c01g0489091;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP2: MtrunA17_Chr0c28g0493951

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr0c28g0493951

Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr0c28g0493951;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP3: MtrunA17_Chr1g0148371

pub/expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr1g0148371

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr1g0148371;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP4: MtrunA17_Chr1g0149991

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr1g0149991;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP5: MtrunA17_Chr1g0150571

pub/expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr1g0150571

Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr1g0150571;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

MtrunA17_Chr1g0150571 [log2_tmm]

*CP6: MtrunA17_Chr1g0152521

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr1g0152521;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP7: MtrunA17_Chr1g0153001

pub/expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr1g0153001

Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr1g0153001;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP8: MtrunA17_Chr1g0155251

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr1g0155251;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP9: MtrunA17_Chr1g0158341

pub/expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr1g0158341

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr1g0158341;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP10: MtrunA17_Chr1g0162101

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr1g0162101;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP11: MtrunA17_Chr1g0164591

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr1g0164591

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr1g0164591;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP12: MtrunA17_Chr1g0178361

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr1g0178361

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr1g0178361;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP13: MtrunA17_Chr1g0181761

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr1g0181761

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr1g0181761;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP14: MtrunA17_Chr1g0182591

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr1g0182591

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr1g0182591;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP15: MtrunA17_Chr1g0183001

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr1g0183001

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr1g0183001;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP16: MtrunA17_Chr1g0185811

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr1g0185811

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr1g0185811;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

MtrunA17_Chr1g0185811 [log2_tmm]

CP17: MtrunA17_Chr1g0185811

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr1g0185811

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr1g0185811;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP18: MtrunA17_Chr1g0185811

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr1g0185811

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr1g0185811;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP19: MtrunA17_Chr1g0185871

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr1g0185871;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

MtExpress V3

Core (20220901)

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

TMM

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GENOME PORTAL

LEGOO

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr1g0190571;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

MtrunA17_Chr1g0190571 [log2_tmm]

CP21: MtrunA17_Chr1g0191411

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr1g0191411

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr1g0191411;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP22: MtrunA17_Chr1g0198091

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr1g0198091

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr1g0198091;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP23: MtrunA17_Chr1g0200071

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr1g0200071

Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr1g0200071;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

MtrunA17_Chr1g0200071 [log2_tmm]

CP24: MtrunA17_Chr1g0200071

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr1g0200071;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

*CP25: MtrunA17_Chr1g0202001

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr1g0202001;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP26: MtrunA17_Chr1g0205601

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr1g0205601

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr1g0205601;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP27: MtrunA17_Chr1g0207811

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr1g0207811

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr1g0207811; MTHAG6

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

*CP28: MtrunA17_Chr1g0207921

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr1g0207921

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr1g0207921;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

MtrunA17_Chr1g0207921 [log2_tmm]

*CP29: MtrunA17_Chr1g0209791

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr1g0209791

Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr1g0209791;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

MtrunA17_Chr1g0209791 [log2_tmm]

CP30: MtrunA17_Chr1g0210521

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr1g0210521

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr1g0210521;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP31: MtrunA17_Chr1g0212961

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr1g0212961

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr1g0212961;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

MtrunA17_Chr1g0212961 [log2_tmm]

ncRNA: MtrunA17_Chr1g1004575;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP33: MtrunA17_Chr2g0283311

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr2g0283311

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr2g0283311;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP34: MtrunA17_Chr2g0285461

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr2g0285461

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr2g0285461; *MtARF6*|*MtARF19a*

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP35: MtrunA17_Chr2g0292921

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr2g0292921;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP36: MtrunA17_Chr2g0298731

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr2g0298731;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP37: MtrunA17_Chr2g0299561

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr2g0299561;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP38: MtrunA17_Chr2g0304891

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

GENOME PORTAL LEGOO

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr2g0304891;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

*CP39: MtrunA17_Chr2g0305951

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr2g0305951

Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr2g0305951;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

MtrunA17_Chr2g0305951 [log2_tmm]

CP40: MtrunA17_Chr2g0309251

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr2g0309251

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr2g0309251;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP41: MtrunA17_Chr2g0310041

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr2g0310041

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr2g0310041;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP42: MtrunA17_Chr2g0312631

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr2g0312631

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr2g0312631;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

MtrunA17_Chr2g0312631 [log2_tmm]

CP43: MtrunA17_Chr2g0316291

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

GENOME PORTAL LEGOO

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr2g0316291;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP44: MtrunA17_Chr2g0326801

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr2g0326801

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr2g0326801;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP45: MtrunA17_Chr2g0328091

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr2g0328091

Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr2g0328091;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP46: MtrunA17_Chr2g0329031

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr2g0329031;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP47: MtrunA17_Chr3g0079521

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr3g0079521;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP48: MtrunA17_Chr3g0083801

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr3g0083801;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP49: MtrunA17_Chr3g0091141

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr3g0091141; MtCKX6

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

*CP50: MtrunA17_Chr3g0091671

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr3g0091671

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr3g0091671;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

MtrunA17_Chr3g0091671 [log2_tmm]

CP51: MtrunA17_Chr3g0096421

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr3g0096421;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

*CP52: MtrunA17_Chr3g0100221

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr3g0100221

Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr3g0100221;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP53: MtrunA17_Chr3g0102171

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr3g0102171;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP54: MtrunA17_Chr3g0105981

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr3g0105981;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP55: MtrunA17_Ch3g0110451

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Ch3g0110451;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP56: MtrunA17_Chr3g0113591

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr3g0113591;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP57: MtrunA17_Chr3g0124631

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr3g0124631

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr3g0124631;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

*CP58: MtrunA17_Chr3g0127321

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr3g0127321

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr3g0127321;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP59: MtrunA17_Chr3g0130671

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr3g0130671;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

MtrunA17_Chr3g0130671 [log2_tmm]

*CP60: MtrunA17_Chr3g0135761

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr3g0135761

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr3g0135761;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP61: MtrunA17_Chr3g0137391

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr3g0137391

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr3g0137391;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP62: MtrunA17_Chr3g0141901

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr3g0141901

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr3g0141901;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP63: MtrunA17_Chr3g0144151

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr3g0144151;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP64: MtrunA17_Chr3g0144151

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr3g0144151

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr3g0144151;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP65: MtrunA17_Chr3g0144151

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr3g0144151

MIExpress V3

Core (20220901)

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

TMM

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GENOME PORTAL

LEGOO

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr3g0144151;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

MtrunA17_Chr3g0144151 [log2_tmm]

ncRNA: MtrunA17_Chr3g1011650;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

MtrunA17_Chr3g1011650 [log2_tmm]

CP67: MtrunA17_Chr4g0000131

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr4g0000131

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr4g0000131;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

*CP68: MtrunA17_Chr4g0000891

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr4g0000891

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr4g0000891;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

MtrunA17_Chr4g0000891 [log2_tmm]

CP69: MtrunA17_Chr4g0004721

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr4g0004721

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr4g0004721;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

*CP70: MtrunA17_Chr4g0014251

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr4g0014251

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr4g0014251;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

MtrunA17_Chr4g0014251 [log2_tmm]

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

GENOME PORTAL LEGOO

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr4g0022491;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

tRNA: MtrunA17_Chr4g0023791;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

MtrunA17_Chr4g0023791 [log2_tmm]

CP73: MtrunA17_Chr4g0034271

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr4g0034271;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP74: MtrunA17_Chr4g0034491

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr4g0034491

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr4g0034491;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP75: MtrunA17_Chr4g0037381

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr4g0037381

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr4g0037381;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP76: MtrunA17_Chr4g0040471

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr4g0040471

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr4g0040471;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

MtrunA17_Chr4g0040471 [log2_tmm]

CP77: MtrunA17_Chr4g0055331

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr4g0055331;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP78: MtrunA17_Chr4g0059001

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr4g0059001;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

*CP79: MtrunA17_Chr4g0063201

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr4g0063201

Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr4g0063201;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

MtrunA17_Chr4g0063201 [log2_tmm]

CP80: MtrunA17_Chr4g0070011

/expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr4g0070011

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr4g0070011; *MtSUCS1*

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

MtrunA17_Chr4g0070011 MtSUCS1 [log2_tmm]

CP81: MtrunA17_Chr5g0393401

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr5g0393401

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr5g0393401; MTHDA9

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP82: MtrunA17_Chr5g0400181

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr5g0400181

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr5g0400181;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP83: MtrunA17_Chr5g0405061

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr5g0405061;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP84: MtrunA17_Chr5g0408581

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr5g0408581

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr5g0408581;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

MtrunA17_Chr5g0408581 [log2_tmm]

CP85: MtrunA17_Chr5g0415031

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr5g0415031;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP86: MtrunA17_Chr5g0415911

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr5g0415911

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr5g0415911;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP87: MtrunA17_Chr5g0421761

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr5g0421761

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

ncRNA: MtrunA17_Chr5g0421761;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

MtrunA17_Chr5g0421761 [log2_tmm]

CP88: MtrunA17_Chr5g0422291

Switch to another dataset using the left menu

GENOME PORTAL LEGOO

rRNA: MtrunA17_Chr5g0422291;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

Switch to another dataset using the left menu

GENOME PORTAL LEGOO

rRNA: MtrunA17_Chr5g0422291;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP90: MtrunA17_Chr5g0430341

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr5g0430341

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr5g0430341;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

MtrunA17_Chr5g0430341 [log2_tmm]

CP91: MtrunA17_Chr5g0430341

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr5g0430341

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr5g0430341;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

MtrunA17_Chr5g0430341 [log2_tmm]

CP92: MtrunA17_Chr5g0431401

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr5g0431401

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr5g0431401;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

MtrunA17_Chr5g0431401 [log2_tmm]

CP93: MtrunA17_Chr5g0435191

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr5g0435191;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP94: MtrunA17_Chr5g0444231

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr5g0444231;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP95: MtrunA17_Chr6g0451601

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr6g0451601;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP96: MtrunA17_Chr6g0452781

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr6g0452781

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr6g0452781;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP97: MtrunA17_Chr6g0457351

Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr6g0457351;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP98: MtrunA17_Chr6g0457461

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr6g0457461;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

MtrunA17_Chr6g0457461 [log2_tmm]

CP99: MtrunA17_Chr6g0457461

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr6g0457461

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr6g0457461;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

MtrunA17_Chr6g0457461 [log2_tmm]

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr6g0457461;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

MtrunA17_Chr6g0457461 [log2_tmm]

CP101: MtrunA17_Chr6g0458091

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr6g0458091

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr6g0458091; MTEF1

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

*CP102: MtrunA17_Chr6g0459481

ExpressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr6g0459481

Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr6g0459481;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP103: MtrunA17_Chr6g0461931

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr6g0461931

Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr6g0461931;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

MtrunA17_Chr6g0461931 [log2_tmm]

CP104: MtrunA17_Chr6g0462271

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr6g0462271

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr6g0462271;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

MtrunA17_Chr6g0462271 [log2_tmm]

*CP105: MtrunA17_Chr6g0468411

ExpressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr6g0468411

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr6g0468411;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP106: MtrunA17_Chr6g0476751

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr6g0476751

MIExpress V3

Core (20220901)

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

📄 TMM METADATA SYNONYMOUS ANNOTATION GENOME PORTAL LEGOO

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr6g0476751;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP107: MtrunA17_Chr6g0479001

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr6g0479001

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr6g0479001;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP108: MtrunA17_Chr6g0485321

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr6g0485321

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr6g0485321;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr6g0486961;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

MtrunA17_Chr6g0486961 [log2_tmm]

CP110: MtrunA17_Chr7g0214741

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr7g0214741

Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr7g0214741;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP111: MtrunA17_Chr7g0214911

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr7g0214911

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr7g0214911;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr7g0221631;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

MtrunA17_Chr7g0221631 [log2_tmm]

CP114: MtrunA17_Chr7g0229401

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr7g0229401

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

rRNA: MtrunA17_Chr7g0229401;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr7g0230341;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

MtrunA17_Chr7g0230341 [log2_tmm]

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr7g0232851; MtSDG53

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

MtrunA17_Chr7g0232851 MtSDG53 [log2_tmm]

CP117: MtrunA17_Chr7g0237331

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr7g0237331

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr7g0237331;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

MtrunA17_Chr7g0237331 [log2_tmm]

*CP118: MtrunA17_Chr7g0251971

ExpressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr7g0251971

Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr7g0251971;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

MtrunA17_Chr7g0251971 [log2_tmm]

CP119: MtrunA17_Chr7g0259611

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr7g0259611

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr7g0259611;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP120: MtrunA17_Chr7g0262821

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr7g0262821

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr7g0262821;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

MtrunA17_Chr7g0262821 [log2_tmm]

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr7g0270811;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

ncRNA: MtrunA17_Chr7g1034306;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

MtrunA17_Chr7g1034306 [log2_tmm]

CP123: MtrunA17_Chr8g0338111

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr8g0338111

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr8g0338111;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

*CP124: MtrunA17_Chr8g0338301

ExpressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr8g0338301

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr8g0338301;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP125: MtrunA17_Chr8g0339891

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr8g0339891

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr8g0339891;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr8g0342881;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

MtrunA17_Chr8g0342881 [log2_tmm]

CP127: MtrunA17_Chr8g0345421

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr8g0345421

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr8g0345421;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

*CP128: MtrunA17_Chr8g0353711

ExpressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr8g0353711

Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr8g0353711;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP129: MtrunA17_Chr8g0355501

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr8g0355501

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr8g0355501;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

MtrunA17_Chr8g0355501 [log2_tmm]

*CP130: MtrunA17_Chr8g0356581

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr8g0356581;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP131: MtrunA17_Chr8g0365341

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr8g0365341

MIExpress V3

Core (20220901)

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

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mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr8g0365341;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

MtrunA17_Chr8g0365341 [log2_tmm]

CP132: MtrunA17_Chr8g0368731

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr8g0368731

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr8g0368731;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP133: MtrunA17_Chr8g0368931

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr8g0368931

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr8g0368931;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP134: MtrunA17_Chr8g0371281

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr8g0371281

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr8g0371281;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

MtrunA17_Chr8g0371281 [log2_tmm]

CP135: MtrunA17_Chr8g0371741

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr8g0371741

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr8g0371741;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP136: MtrunA17_Chr8g0373091

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr8g0373091

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr8g0373091;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP137: MtrunA17_Chr8g0376411

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr8g0376411

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr8g0376411;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP138: MtrunA17_Chr8g0377071

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr8g0377071

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr8g0377071;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

MtrunA17_Chr8g0377071 [log2_tmm]

CP139: MtrunA17_Chr8g0385331

expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_Chr8g0385331

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_Chr8g0385331;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

ncRNA: MtrunA17_Chr8g0392351;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP141: MtrunA17_CPg0492331

pub/expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_CPg0492331

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

rRNA: MtrunA17_CPg0492331;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP142: MtrunA17_CPg0492381

pub/expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_CPg0492381

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

ncRNA: MtrunA17_CPg0492381;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP143: MtrunA17_CPg0492461

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_CPg0492461;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP144: MtrunA17_CPg0492851

pub/expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_CPg0492851

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_CPg0492851;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

MtrunA17_CPg0492851 [log2_tmm]

CP145: MtrunA17_CPg0492941

pub/expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_CPg0492941

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_CPg0492941;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

CP146: MtrunA17_CPg0493291

pub/expressionAtlas/app/v3/aa_reference_dataset/MtrunA17_CPg0493291

! Switch to another dataset using the left menu

mRNA: MtrunA17_CPg0493291;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

mRNA: MtrunA17_CPg0493401;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

mRNA: MtrunA17_MTg0490471;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

mRNA: MtrunA17_MTg0490471;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

ncRNA: MtrunA17_MTg0490971;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

MtrunA17_MTg0490971 [log2_tmm]

ncRNA: MtrunA17_MTg0490971;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

ncRNA: MtrunA17_MTg0491151;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

mRNA: MtrunA17_MTg0491291;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

ncRNA: MtrunA17_MTg0491501;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

ncRNA: MtrunA17_MTg0491621;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

ncRNA: MtrunA17_MTg0491711;

Log2 TMM Normalisation using EdgeR (Core [20220901])

Supplementary Dataset S27. Expression profiles of 156 primary-source transcripts. Screenshots are from the RNA-Seq-based gene expression atlas of *Medicago truncatula* (MtExpress v. 3, <https://medicago.toulouse.inrae.fr/GEA>). For clarity and better visibility, only the core sample set is shown. Chimeric peptide identifiers that begin with an asterisk correspond to transcripts with log₂ TMM values below zero.